

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Figure S1. Gating strategy used for flow cytometry analysis of monocyte surface markers. *CytoFLEX S* flow cytometer (Beckman Coulter Life Sciences, Indianapolis, IN, USA) was used for both monocytes phenotype and polarization.

Figure S2. Example of monocytes culture after 24h exposure to various conditions. *LPS* : lipopolysaccharide; *POLY (I:C)* polyinosinic:polycytidylic acid; *IL-10* : interleukin-10

Table S1. Complete blood count before and 2h after KE consumption

Variables	T0	T120	P values
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	6.25 \pm 1.50	6.98 \pm 1.93	0.006
Neutrophils ($\times 10^9/L$)	3.24 \pm 1.17	4.05 \pm 1.58	0.001
Lymphocytes ($\times 10^9/L$)	2.31 \pm 0.71	2.21 \pm 0.65	0.964
Monocytes ($\times 10^9/L$)	0.49 \pm 0.13	0.52 \pm 0.17	0.451
Neutrophils (%)	51.0 \pm 8.5	56.8 \pm 9.1	0.001
Lymphocytes (%)	37.4 \pm 8.7	32.5 \pm 8.0	0.003
Monocytes (%)	8.0 \pm 1.6	7.5 \pm 1.5	0.003
RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	4.73 \pm 0.47	4.96 \pm 0.50	0.001
HGB (g/dL)	14.17 \pm 1.87	15.20 \pm 1.70	0.001
HCT (%)	41.7 \pm 4.7	44.4 \pm 4.5	0.002
MCV (femtoliters)	88.2 \pm 7.6	89.7 \pm 5.9	0.689
Platelet ($\times 10^9/L$)	250.8 \pm 52.4	244.2 \pm 52.2	0.182

Data are presented as mean \pm SD; WBC: white blood cells; RBC: red blood cells; HGB: hemoglobin; HCT: hematocrit; MCV: mean corpuscular volume; Bold denotes a significant difference pre (T0) compared to 2 hours (T120) after exogenous ketone consumption.

Figure S3. Poly I:C stimulation of whole blood and monocyte cultures before and after exogenous ketone consumption

Data are presented as box-and-whisker plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum values with individual participants' data; A: POLY I:C-stimulated whole blood culture before (T0) and after (T120) exogenous ketone exposure in vivo; B: POLY I:C-stimulated monocytes culture before (T0) and after (T120) exogenous ketone exposure in vivo.

Figure S4. IL-10-mediated anti-inflammatory response with and without in vivo exposure to BHB

Data are presented as box-and-whisker plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum values with individual participants' data; A: LPS-stimulated whole blood culture (4h) with and without 1 and 10 ng/dL of IL-10 before (T0) and after (T120) exogenous ketone exposure in vivo; B: LPS-stimulated monocytes culture (24h) with and without 1 and 10 ng/dL of IL-10 before (T0) and after (T12) exogenous ketone exposure in vivo.

Figure S5. Monocyte Phenotypes Following 24h Exposure to LPS With or Without IL-10 and BHB

Data are presented as box-and-whisker plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum values with individual participants' data; A: CD80+ MFI after 24h culture; B: CD163+ MFI after 24h culture; C: CD14+ MFI after 24h culture.